

SHORT STORY "WHO IS UNDER EIGHTEEN": INTERPRETATION OF HUMAN FATE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the interpretation of human fate in Shukur Kholmirzaev's short story "Who is under Eighteen?" The story's relevance in today's youth education, and how the issue of reading influences the spirituality of the characters, is examined.*

Keywords: *artistic intent, creative process, powerful writer, trend, worldview of characters, artistic analysis, artistic image, artistic intent, inner world of the characters, artistic skill, love, consequence, deviation, and destiny, Sangardak, Yetim tog', Farhod tog'i, Ketmon Chopti, love triangle.*

Shukur Kholmirzaev as a distinctive literary stylist avoids criticism, one-sidedness, and narration in his works. While he is a master of words, he strives only to convey meaning to the reader in a clear and vivid way. However, sometimes his works leave the impression that they are unfinished. Readers tend to wait for a continuation. He does not create portraits of characters. It seems that the main focus is on developing the characters' personalities, which forces the reader to think deeply and critically. The judgment on the characters is left to the reader's attention.

When examining the creative process from Shukur Kholmirzaev's initial views on the truth of life to his most recent works, one can more clearly see the factors that influenced the formation of his creative principles. The writer's unique talent stands out as the primary and key factor. Kholmirzaev entered literature with his stories "Oq Otli" and "To'lqinlar" and was able to demonstrate that he had great poetic potential even within the narrow confines of the short story.

The short story "Who is under Eighteen?" was published in the 10th issue of the *Sharq Yulduzi* magazine in 1965. On September 9, 1965, at the Writers' Union, during a republic seminar-discussion of young writers' prose section, the story was discussed. In the speech by the deputy chairman of the Writers' Union, Asqad Muxtor, the following was noted: "Another direct aspect of talent and mastery is style. In this regard, Shukur Kholmirzaev's works offer interesting material. I recently read his story 'Who is under Eighteen?' The thing that draws attention to this author is his uniqueness. Right from the first work, attracting attention with individual characteristics is a significant achievement. The most important thing is that this uniqueness comes from the deep understanding of the specifics of figurative thinking.

Kholmirzaev enhances the imagery with very detailed descriptions, without directly intervening in the narrative. He works with words as a painter does with paints, using fine brushes. You don't read, you observe a picture. The story seems to consist of many pictures. Each episode is like a painting, with its own composition and internal plot." [6]

Asqad Muxtor notes that Kholmirzaev's chosen style is responsible, requiring keen observation, attention to the details of life, and a specific eye, memory, taste, and the ability to focus on the details. He also acknowledges that Kholmirzaev's original approach has its flaws. When it comes to the portrayal of human relationships and the emotional world, the "paints"

(descriptions) are sometimes insufficient. The author's personal style tends to lose its effect when it cannot capture the full scope of social themes. The limitations of the style become evident, indicating that both the author and the reader must critically analyze and consider expanding the stylistic possibilities." [6]

Three months after the seminar, in the article "On the Path of Naturalism" by Umarali Normatov, it is clear that the ideas expressed are very much in line with Asqad Muxtor's critique.

"Who is under Eighteen?" is considered one of the autobiographical works of the author. The story is inspired by events in the life of the writer's elder brother Tura aka and the hardships his family faced. The characters in the story, such as Jamshid (Shukur Kholmirzaev), Tilov (Tura aka), Zaynabxon (the writer's mother), Jalolov (Orziqul Polvon), and Muslima buvi (Ruxsat momo), become the closest conversationalists for the reader.

Regarding the character of Muslima buvi, her past is described as follows: "At the age of twenty-five, Muslima buvi was left with two children—daughter Zaynabxon and son Abdukarim. (Her husband died while fighting against the enemies.) At that time, this place was barren land. Afterward, the elderly woman did not remarry and dedicated the rest of her life to raising her two children and cultivating the land for them."

Muslima buvi spent her days working tirelessly in the fields, planting trees during the day, and weaving and taking care of her children at night. Over the years, both her orchard and her children grew. However, one of her children followed in his father's footsteps and tragically died while fighting the fascist invaders. Zaynabxon, on the other hand, led a very different life, one that seemed restless—constantly moving between towns, often absent for long periods, especially during the years of war. At one point, she even became the head of a collective farm. Muslima buvi always remained loyal to the land, her family, and her legacy. [9, 9]

In this story, the author recalls his father, Fayzullo Kholmirzaev, with deep sorrow and longing. Jamshid (Shukur) hardly ever heard his father's voice, but he was certain that his father—who had gone off to fight the fascists—would return one day. When Jamshid's father left, Jamshid was still an infant in a cradle: "On the day he left, his grandmother took him to the door. His father threw him into the air and said, 'I will come back. You will grow up.'" [9, 29]

The narrative of the story mostly takes place within Muslima buvi's yard. The author nostalgically depicts his youthful memories, filling them with a deep sense of longing and love. The childhood of Jamshid, Zaynabxon's role as a party secretary of the "Victory" collective farm, and the relationship dynamics between the family members, particularly between Jamshid and his uncle Jalolov, provide a vivid portrayal of familial relationships and complex emotions. These moments are not figments of the author's imagination but an artistic reflection of real-life events.

After writing "*Who Is Under Eighteen?*" Shukur Kholmirzaev stopped writing for seven years. During this period, he immersed himself in world literature, reading works from India, France, England, and partially Italian literature. He was particularly drawn to American literature and even explored Latin American works. After reading these works, he reflected on the political manipulations, nationalism, racism, and imperialism that were prevalent, while humans remained unchanged. He stated, "*It was then that I realized that I should not serve political ideologies. It is human's fate that must be depicted. One must listen to the heart of man...*" [8, 90]

The portrayal of Muslima buvi's mixed emotions towards her new son-in-law, Jalolov, is captured in the following passage: "*How could a man with a house, respect, and a reputation come to live with us as a son-in-law?*" [9, 36] she thought to herself. Jalolov, however, appeared

indifferent to the situation and behaved freely, as though moving from one home to another. Muslima buvi eventually accepted him, thinking, *"His nature is broad,"* and began to warm to him. [9, 36]

Literary scholar L. Qayumov, in his analysis of works published in 1965, discussed Shukur Kholmiraev's *"Who is Under Eighteen?"* by noting how the story introduced endearing and realistic characters such as Umida, Jamshid, and Tilov to the gallery of literary figures. Through their relationships and fates, the author presented the early steps of independent life, the missteps of youth, first love, and its allure. Qayumov praised Kholmiraev's psychological observation skills, noting how the author credibly portrayed the inner world of youth. In the writer's style, he emphasized the strength of realism and naturalism. [7, 55]

The author reflects on Ernest Hemingway's belief: *"A good writer is a good person, and a bad person can never be a good writer."* Kholmiraev's story shows that the characters he writes about are reflections of himself, and only through understanding oneself can a writer authentically depict others. In his story, Kholmiraev masterfully presents the internal and external struggles of the youth, reflecting on their ideals, dreams, and battles with life.

In terms of its compositional structure, *"Who Is Under Eighteen?"* seeks to break new ground, experimenting with innovative approaches. The author explores not only the dreams and aspirations of the Uzbek people but also the hidden struggles and emotional complexities of youth. His characters are unique—sometimes naive, sometimes rebellious, but always full of depth. They are loyal to their heritage, their country, their values, and their beliefs. They fight for justice and truth but never do so with boastful grandiosity. Instead, they approach life with sincerity, warmth, and empathy.

Kholmiraev's story does not provide easy answers, nor does it offer a tidy conclusion. Instead, he presents life as it is—complicated, unresolved, and deeply human. The readers are left to reflect on the fates of the characters, experiencing their joy, sorrow, and struggles as if they were their own. *"Who is Under Eighteen?"* continues to resonate with readers even after decades because of its portrayal of love, loss, fate, and the resilience of youth. Though the theme of love is central to the story, it also delves into the complexities of relationships, youth's idealism, and the inevitable disillusionments of growing up.

In conclusion, Shukur Kholmiraev's *"Who is Under Eighteen?"* is a profound literary work that transcends mere storytelling. It is a rich, psychological exploration of youth, identity, and human emotion, resonating deeply with readers and continuing to captivate audiences for decades. The story's sincerity and truth make it an enduring piece of Uzbek literature.

The writer attempts to reveal the painful traces and sufferings left by the war on people's destinies, especially through the character of Muslima Buvi. When Muslima Buvi's husband was killed fighting the enemies in the war, she was only twenty-five years old. She had two children: her daughter Zaynabkhon and her son Abdukarim. The war left this young woman widowed early, causing her to experience the sorrow of losing a father figure and forcing her children, who had not yet felt their father's love, to face the pain of orphanhood. In one family, the writer illustrates how an entire nation suffers through these dark days. The reader, upon reading about Muslima Buvi's tragic fate and her sole reliance on her willpower to survive, inevitably begins to condemn the war. The death of Muslima Buvi's only son in the fight against the fascists, despite her perseverance in her life, is depicted skillfully. Furthermore, in the story told by Hojiyev about "Iskandar's campaign," the writer shows the negative consequences of the war. The reader

witnesses how well the writer knows the history of the region he lived in, especially through place names such as Sangardak, Yetim Tog‘, Farhod Tog‘i, Ketmon Chopti, which are presented through the characters’ dialogue.

Farhod supposedly went up the mountain to draw water. At that time, our Sangardak was a dry desert. Farhod struck a pickaxe at the mountain and when he looked down, he saw a big river flowing beneath. Where did this river come from? Farhod did not know that it was the river Yosuman Buvai had created by spreading her birch tree branches. To Farhod, it appeared as a river. He, in turn, made a bet with Yosuman and ended up killing himself. The mountain’s name remains as Farhod, and the place where Farhod struck his pickaxe is called Ketmon Chopti. If we closely observe the main characters of the story, we can deeply sense the emotional state of the characters caught in a love triangle. The writer’s success lies in his ability to vividly convey these feelings. This story differs from other works that praise love in that the characters’ personalities, worldview, and spirituality are all shaped by the books they read. First, the fate of two orphans intersects: Jamshid’s mother, Zaynabkhon, marries Tilov’s father, Jalolov, and these children, with different bloodlines, become like siblings. Through the plot of this story, Shukur Xolmirzayev invites the reader to observe the sequence of events carefully.

There has always been a negative attitude toward stepmothers and stepfathers in folk culture. However, in this story, Shukur Xolmirzayev challenges this view, showing that even stepmothers and stepfathers can be loving and kind. He illustrates through Zaynabkhon and Jalolov that despite not being biological parents, there are compassionate and caring figures who take on the role of loving parents.

The names of several books and their characters are mentioned in the story. The characters’ desire to imitate these literary figures—especially Umida, who dreams of playing the tragic roles of Katerina, Jamila, and Nina—demonstrates how deeply the characters’ lives are influenced by the books they read. Eventually, Umida’s life echoes the tragic fate of the characters she admires.

In conclusion, Shukur Xolmirzayev was not only a prominent figure in literature but also a person with strong principles and a distinct worldview. His thoughts on literature and life compel readers to reflect on their own lives. He was a true creator who valued literature above all else. His works highlight characters who could not imagine living without literature, making it clear how deeply literature shaped his life and thoughts. When reading his works, one can sense how his love for literature and the warmth of life resonates through his words. The landscapes and vibrant settings in his stories reflect the living, breathing nature of the world he cherished.

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